

CULTURE SHOCK

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Annotation; in this article, there are some troubles which related to culture shock. You may see the types of culture shock and likewise its own meaning, examples and so on.

Key words; culture, culture shock, honeymoon, frustration, adjustment, acceptance, manifests.

Introduction

It is an indisputable fact that Culture shock is a normal process of adapting to a new culture. It is a time when a person becomes aware of the differences and/or conflicts in values and customs between their home culture and the new culture they are in. Common feelings may be anxiety, confusion, homesickness.

Such as, culture shock is some sort of adjustment you might feel when you are subject to a new way of living and an unfamiliar setting around you. Culture shock is feeling uncomfortable or sometimes even lonely when you are abroad in a new place (for example, during family holidays like Christmas). It might take a bit of time to settle (first two weeks are usually the most intense).

There is not anything, in particular, that might cause it, however rather a mixture of new habits you come across when you move overseas: unknown greetings (for example, in France the most common greeting among members of the family is the 'la bise' (kiss on both cheeks), local customs, accents you are not used to, or unusual food. The unknown can be overwhelming and might lead to making a cultural faux pas or feeling confused, anxious, lonely or unconfident. In essence, it might cause you stress.

It tends to impact travelers even after they've become familiar with and comfortable in new cultures. Culture shock generally moves through four different phases: honeymoon, frustration, adjustment, and acceptance. Individuals experience these stages differently, and the impact and order of each stage vary widely.

Honeymoon; A honeymoon is a vacation taken by newlyweds immediately after their wedding, to celebrate their marriage. Today, honeymoons are often celebrated in destinations considered exotic or romantic. In a similar context, it may also refer to the phase in a couple's

relationship - whether they are in matrimony or not - that exists before getting used to everyday life together.

ALTHEXPAT LIFE

Frustration; A frustration is a common emotional response to opposition, related to anger, annoyance and disappointment. Frustration arises from the perceived resistance to the fulfillment of an individual's will or goal and is likely to increase when a will or goal is denied or blocked. There are two types of frustration: internal and external. Internal frustration may arise from challenges in fulfilling personal goals, desires, instinctual drives and needs, or dealing with perceived deficiencies, such as a lack of confidence or fear of social situations. Conflict, such as when one has competing goals that interfere with one another, can also be an internal source of frustration or annoyance and can create cognitive dissonance. External causes of frustration involve conditions outside an individual's control, such as a physical roadblock, a difficult task, or the perception of wasting time. There are multiple ways individuals cope with frustration such as passive-aggressive behavior, anger, or violence, although frustration may also propel positive processes via enhanced effort and strive. This broad range of potential outcomes makes it difficult to identify the original cause(s) of frustration, as the responses may be indirect. However, a more direct and common response is a propensity towards aggression

Adjustment; The act of making an alteration or modification is an adjustment. If you buy a new pair of jeans, but they are too long, you can make a quick adjustment and hem them, have someone else hem them, or use safety pins. ... The process of adapting to your environmental conditions is also called an adjustment. After you leave home for college, both you and your parents will have a period of adjustment.

Acceptance; The term acceptance is a noun with various different meanings. When the person to whom a proposal is made signifies their assent, it is an "acceptance" of their offer, also called an agreement. For example, if someone gives a gift and another receives it, then they have accepted the gift; therefore, having acceptance. Another definition of acceptance has to do with positive welcome and belonging, favor, and endorsement. One approves of something. For instance, one can like someone and accept them due to their approval of that person. Another description is that acceptance can be an act of believing or assenting. The definition overlaps with toleration, but acceptance and tolerance are not synonyms.

Acceptance – "An express act or implication by conduct that manifests assent to the terms of an offer in a manner invited or required by the offer so that a binding contract is formed. The exercise of power conferred by an offer by performance of some act. The act of a person to whom something is offered or tendered by another, whereby the offered demonstrates through an act invited by the offer an intention of retaining the subject of the offer."

By way of conclusion, it is process of adapting to a new culture. It is a time when a person becomes aware of the differences and/or conflicts in values and customs between their home culture and the new culture they are in. Common feelings may be anxiety, confusion, homesickness. In this case, human supposed to figure out any issue in any place.

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